

Stakeholder Engagement

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Who are the Digital Repository of Ireland?

Leaders in Digital Preservation, Access and Discovery

- A digital preservation repository for Ireland's cultural heritage, humanities and social science data
- A member-based organization (58)
- Funded by DFHERIS through the HEA

Why is stakeholder engagement important to DRI?

- Member organisation- engagement with material is a service
- Research performing organisation- we want people to engage with our research
- We generate policies and standards-we want people to use them
- FAIR- driving re-use
- We are publicly funded

What are the key policies for driving engagement with stakeholders?

- DRI Engagement strategy, 2019-2024 (internal)
- DRI Equality, Diversity and Inclusion Policy, 2023-2026 (external)
- DRI Strategic Plan, 2025-2029 (external)

Who are DRI's stakeholders?

- Our Members
- Users of the Repository (front end)
- Depositors to the Repository
- The Irish Research Community
- Other Researchers interested in Ireland
- The Irish Public
- Our Funders
- Our staff
- Our administrating institutions

Stakeholder Engagement: Where to start?

Identify your stakeholders

- There are lots of useful templates to help you identify your stakeholders
- This may allow you to make decisions on how much you need to engage your stakeholders and how important they are (not all stakeholders are the same!)
- It will help you see the big picture and think about the purpose of Engagement

Engagement should be tailored

‘User’ profiles can help

- Create a profile for each stakeholder

Think about them-

- What are they interested in?
- What are their priorities?
- Why do they need you?

Why are you trying to engage them-

- What are you trying to tell them?
- What’s the best way to communicate to them?
- How can you convey impact to them?

What's in our engagement strategy?

- Who do we want to engage?
- What is the purpose of engagement?
- Comms channels (and how useful they are)
- What are the resources that you need for engagement
- Feedback templates
- Engagement metrics
- Impact case studies
- Event/project close out templates

What does good stakeholder engagement look like to you?

- Break down the component parts of your programme and engage in some planning.
- Do you have the resources that you need for this to work well?
- When did you feel like a valued stakeholder and why was that?
- Is there anything missing in your plan?
- Are you being too ambitious?
- It might be worth taking a multi-phased approach- start small or even try a pilot.
- See what works well before undertaking something really big.

A recent success- what does good engagement look like?

DPASSH June 2024 (Digital Preservation of Arts, Social Science and Humanities)

- We collaborated with two new national partners (University of Limerick and the Hunt Museum)
- We found a new regional audience
- We gained a new member (Limerick City and County Council)
- We had our highest conference numbers
- We broke even on our event!

Why did it work well?

- We reviewed the previous conferences event close out document
- We formed our programme and organising committee
- We identified the audience we wanted to engage and we targeted them
- We had a good lead in time (planning!)
- We got input from our regional partners
- We had some really creative elements that people loved

Poor Engagement

- DRI's Early Career Research Award- ran in 2019, 2020 and 2021 (MA and PhD students)
- Aim was to reward data re-use by making a €500 award to an early career researcher who was re-using our collection
- Ceased in 2022 due to lack of engagement

What went wrong?

- Were we doing enough to help drive re-use before making an award? Was re-use happening at *this* ECR stage?

We are now looking at re-engaging with a different criteria and with training sessions

Other things to think about...

Is it appropriate to think about a stakeholder forum?

They can take lots of forms...

- A kick off project meeting with stakeholders to help them shape the design of a project
- An annual feedback day
- A coffee morning (online or in-person)
- A world café-style event
- A facilitated-feedback session (get someone external to run it)

What stories do you want to tell?

RIA Acadamh Ríoga na hÉireann
Royal Irish Academy

**Member
Case Study**

Developing
preservation pathways
for physically published
legacy materials.

dri

DCU

**Member
Case Study**

Transferring collections from
local network storage to
long-term digital preservation
- and leveraging Europeana

dri

CORK LGBT ARCHIVE

**Member
Case Study**

Digitally preserving a critically
endangered community archive

dri

Do something fun!

Final, final, thoughts...

- Be clear about what you want to tell your stakeholders (test your ‘elevator pitch’)
- Be friendly
- Be prepared to listen
- Go to meet them (they will appreciate the gesture)
- Try something new- it’s worth if you succeed.

Thank you!

13. Sealing the packed Tins.

Jacob's Biscuit Factory. *Sealing the packed tins.* Image [Type]. Digital Repository of Ireland (2019) [Publisher]. Dublin City Library and Archive [Depositor]. <https://doi.org/10.7486/DRI.2z119913q> (Accessed: 2024/06/05)